

What Constitutes a Constitution?

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Abstract

As organizations develop, they will often attempt to codify their cultures by drafting formal, written constitutions – making it apparent, in the process, that the understanding of the structure and function of constitutions that they are invoking is too reductive to reliably result in the desired outcome. In identifying the constitutive function across different contexts, we clarify the understanding of this integral function as more ubiquitous than its commonly-understood nation-state expressions might indicate.

This article outlines an alternative way to conceptualize an organization’s “constitution” – namely, as the institutional infrastructure that manifests and entrenches the boundaries between that organization and its environment. This more robust understanding of the structure and function of constitutions can provide novel answers to the unique set of questions posed by the governance of distributed networks – and to the broader question of what actually constitutes a constitution.

Image generated with Deep.AI. Prompt “Constitutional Design in Decentralized Autonomous Organizations”

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What is a Constitution?

If one looks up the word “constitution” in the dictionary,¹ one finds an array of interrelated but distinct definitions:

- 1a: the basic principles and laws of a nation, state, or social group that determine the powers and duties of the government and guarantee certain rights to the people in it
- 1b: a written instrument embodying the rules of a political or social organization
- 2a: the physical makeup of the individual especially with respect to the health, strength, and appearance of the body
- 2b: the structure, composition, physical makeup, or nature of something
- 3: the mode in which a state or society is organized. especially: the manner in which sovereign power is distributed
- 4: an established law or custom
- 5: the act of establishing, making, or setting up

It is impossible to proceed without clarifying the relationships between these seven senses of the term. We begin by folding **Definition 4** (“an established law or custom”) into **Definition 5** (“the act of establishing, making, or setting up”) and differentiate them from the other remaining definitions, insofar as **5** names a process, rather than offering any insight into what the product of that process is, while **4** names one of the products of that process without providing the requisite context. From here, the picture clarifies substantially: **Definition 2b** (“the structure, composition, physical makeup, or nature of something”) is an umbrella concept, under which **Definition 2a** (“the physical makeup of the individual especially with respect to the health, strength, and appearance of the body”) clearly falls. **Definition 1a** (“the basic principles and laws of a nation, state, or social group that determine the powers and duties of the government and guarantee certain rights to the people in it”) and **Definition 3** (“the mode in which a state or society is organized especially: the manner in which sovereign power is distributed”) are also both subsets of Definition 2b — which makes sense, as **1a** and **3** are two ways of saying the same thing. Finally, **Definition 1b** (“a written instrument embodying the rules of a political or social organization”) is a special case of the general concept identified in definitions **1a** and **3**.

In other words, *the first thing that most people think of when they hear the word “constitution” is in fact the most limited (and limiting) sense of the word.* Clearly, our existing understanding of constitutions is quite jumbled: Per the schema above, it is possible to talk about a formal, written constitution (**1b**) being part of an organization’s overall social constitution (**1a/3**), which is in turn part of the general constitution (**2b**) of that organization — and all of these constitutions are themselves the products of a process called “constitution” (**5**). In order to say anything nuanced about this topic (or any other), however, one must first have unique terms with which to refer to its component parts.

In our multidisciplinary research, we have found that the confusion around constitutions can be readily resolved by first “zooming out” — that is, reformulating our understanding of the concept with a greater degree of generalization — and then “zooming back in” by subjecting this new understanding to a functional decomposition.

¹<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/constitution>. Accessed 3/30/2023.

To begin this process, we will start with the existing definition with the highest degree of generality — **2b**: “the structure, composition, physical makeup, or nature of something.” Keeping **2a** (“the physical makeup of the individual especially with respect to the health, strength, and appearance of the body”) in the back of our minds, due to its conceptual proximity to our primary definition (1a), we then recast these definitions in functional terms: If the existing definitions try (and fail) to tell us what a constitution is, we will reformulate them in such a way that they instead tell us what a constitution does. In this case, we would say that *In this case, we would say that an organization’s constitution structures, composes, physically makes up, or determines the nature of that organization.*

Put differently, **The function of a constitution is to delineate the boundaries of a particular organization, entrenching elements of its composition relative to the organization’s regular processes of decision-making, as well as against the broader array of legal, social, economic, and environmental forces that make up its context(s). This constitutive function operates to reinforce the coherence of the organization in the face of both internal and external pressures, such that it can dynamically evolve through its interactions with both its members and its environment while nonetheless retaining its identity.**

This definition applies equally to entities as it does organizations, although the decision-making processes that a given entity’s constitution bounds may vary considerably more because of the broader class of things that can be deemed entities relative to organizations. Indeed, the broader class of complex entities to which the constitutive function applies is a point central to our exposition here, notwithstanding the necessarily ubiquitous association between organizations and this same constitutive function.

Once we identify the above as the function of constitutions (which we will refer to as the *constitutive* function), it becomes apparent that the dictionary’s varied definitions of the word are simply an array of possible *implementations* of this constitutive function. “[T]he basic principles and laws of a nation, state, or social group that determine the powers and duties of the government and guarantee certain rights to the people in it” are the most obvious *mechanisms* through which organizations of the types named demarcate certain of their characteristics as *constitutive*. This entrenches them at a level that cannot be modified without going outside that organization’s regular process; fractally, “a written instrument embodying the rules of a political or social organization” is simply a particular form that these mechanisms can take.

An organization’s *constitutive infrastructure* consists of all of that organization’s implementations of the constitutive function, accounting for the relationships between these implementations.² Like all infrastructures, constitutive infrastructures have *some* elements that can be architected — deliberately designed in order to ensure that they fulfill the requisite functions and fit to a given organization’s context. For example, written, formal constitutional documents are a form of constitutive infrastructure that history has shown to be particularly well-suited to the needs of centralized nation-states. These written documents serve to constitute both legal and cultural elements of the nation-state. Nonetheless, nation-states are composed of other (privately and publicly administered) civil infrastructures such as power grids, banking systems and religious organizations (to name just a few). Plainly,

²In the context of blockchain systems, some examples of constitutive infrastructure include software code, written documentation, social norms, and legal documentation.

the nation-state is embodied by a host of distinct but interrelated infrastructures and institutions.

In the context of blockchain communities, software is a primary constitutive infrastructure. Blockchain-based smart contracts are a particularly potent constitutive infrastructure precisely because they can be *implemented, administered and enforced uniformly via executable code*, rather than implemented through written documents, administered by a bureaucracy and enforced by a legal system. These particular properties of blockchain networks make them suitable for infrastructuring procedural elements of an organization’s constitutive function.³ This stands in contrast to the often nebulous “social contract” which arguably binds constituents irrespective of their consent. In many cases, these alternative mechanisms for “constituting” a community will prove better-suited to that community’s specific situation, needs, and aspirations than would a formal, written constitution.

Contextualizing the Constitutive Function

The elements that make up an organization’s constitutive infrastructure will, by definition, contribute to the process of *constituting* that organization’s internal and external boundaries. This process, however, can be further broken down into subsidiary processes: Determining which **people** are (and by extension, are not) subject to the organization’s governance, mapping the **environment** that the organization operates within, and defining the **purpose** that animates the organization, motivating the ways that its people interact with its environment.⁴

People refers to an organization’s *internal context* — who it includes, how it structures the interactions between members, and the pressures that these elements exert on the organization’s boundaries from within. The organization in question draws an external boundary separating its constituent members (or “body politic”) from outsiders, by defining criteria for citizenship, membership, and/or participation. At the same time, the diversity of values, desires, and skills found among the constituent members of a given organization exerts an influence on the shape of an organization’s internal boundaries — a well-constituted organization is one with a constitutive infrastructure that adequately and accurately embodies the values and wants of its members.⁵

Environment, on the other hand, refers to an organization’s *external contexts* — that is, everything that remains distinct from an organization once it is constituted. An organization’s environment exerts various forms of pressure (i.e. regulatory, legal, economic, cultural, etc.) on the shape of an organization’s boundaries *from without* — and, to the extent that the external environment influences how the organization chooses to conduct itself, it is able to exert pressure on the shape of the organization’s internal boundaries, as well.

Finally, an organization’s **Purpose** can be thought of as its *mediating context* — that is, as the set of attractors that orient the exercise of the various mechanisms through which the organization mediates the relationships between its internal and external contexts. When information flows from that organization’s environment to its people,

³Nabben, Kelsie. (2023). Web3 as ‘self-infrastructuring’: The challenge is how. *Big Data & Society*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517231159002>

⁴Alston, Eric. “Animating Purpose, Governance as Conflict & Institutional Incompleteness.” (2022). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0roh5AM0iw>

⁵Thornhill, Chris. “Constitutionalism: Sociology Of.” In *Encyclopedia of the Philosophy of Law and Social Philosophy*, edited by Mortimer Sellers and Stephan Kirste, 1–9. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6730-0_72-1.

its purpose informs its interpretation of that information; when information flows from its people to its environment, the organization’s purpose informs its choices (which may in turn affect its environment), and the manner of its transmission. An organization’s purpose is temporally mediating, as well; an organization moves towards its purpose *through* time.

People, Environment and Purpose collectively define the circumstances in which an organization constitutes itself. A constitutive infrastructure manifests and entrenches a boundary between People and Environment, mediating activity pursuant to purpose. *Infrastructures* by their nature enable a set of other activities, and they evolve on a slower timescale than the activities they enable.⁶ Different kinds of constitutive infrastructures may have markedly different modalities for change. For example, written constitutions have “secondary rules” — the *rules governing governance and its procedures* — while software products have *version control*⁷ and *Continuous-Integration Continuous-Deployment* (CI/CD) frameworks⁸. What is important to recognize about both of these mechanisms for change is that they are entrenched more deeply than the infrastructures they modify. Mechanisms for adapting constitutive infrastructures may also be referred to as *Governance Surfaces*.⁹

Provisioning Constitutive Infrastructures

The understanding of constitutions offered in this article makes it clear that written constitutions are just one kind of constitutive infrastructure, which encompasses a significantly wider range of social and technical mechanisms. **Thus, it becomes apparent that many blockchain communities currently considering a formal, written constitution have already constituted — they have already developed significant constitutive infrastructure through their code, protocols, social norms, and the emergent process of institutional ordering that is governance itself.**¹⁰

In cases where such an infrastructure is already fulfilling the constitutive function for an organization, there may be no benefit to translating an organization’s already-existing constitutive infrastructure into a more formal “Constitution” as a document external to the existing processes that already constitute the organization. Insofar as there are identifiable gaps in the constitutive function, it may be appropriate to provision additional constitutive infrastructures, but before doing so, constitutional designers for blockchain networks must be attentive to the existing balance of constitutive forces we have defined.

The pre-existing constitutive forces determine the scope and form of additional constitutive infrastructure that is possible, let alone desirable for a given organization. Constitutional best practices are therefore organization-specific to a great extent, and can directly implicate regulatory liability depending upon the tokenization or capitalization of the organization in question.

⁶C.R. Hinings, D. M. Logue, and C. Zietsma. “Fields, institutional infrastructure and governance.” The Sage handbook of organisational institutionalism. 2017.

⁷Rochkind, Marc J. (1975). “The Source Code Control System”. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering. SE-1 (4): 364–370. doi:10.1109/TSE.1975.6312866

⁸Gallaba, Keheliya (2019). “Improving the Robustness and Efficiency of Continuous Integration and Deployment”. 2019 IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution (ICSME): 619–623. doi:10.1109/ICSME.2019.00099. ISBN 978-1-7281-3094-1. S2CID 208879679.

⁹Zargham, Michael and Nabben, Kelsie, Aligning ‘Decentralized Autonomous Organization’ to Precedents in Cybernetics (April 4, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4077358> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4077358>

¹⁰Alston, “Animating Purpose.” Forthcoming article.

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Further reading:

Alston, Eric, An Organizational Coase Theorem: Constitutional Constraints as Increasing in Exit Costs (February 21, 2022). Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4039320>

Alston, E. (2022). Governance as Conflict: Constitution of Shared Values Defining Future Margins of Disagreement. MIT Computational Law Report. Retrieved from <https://law.mit.edu/pub/governanceasconflict>;

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